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Research Article

**COMPARISON OF ARTHROSCOPIC AND CLINICAL
FINDINGS IN MENISCAL TEARS**Dr Muhammad Wajid Rasool¹, Dr Tauqeer Hussain Khan², Dr Tahir Ameer Malik³^{1,2} Nishtar Medical University and Hospital, Multan³ Bengbu Medical College, Anhui Province, China**Article Received:** April 2020**Accepted:** May 2020**Published:** June 2020**Abstract:**

Aim: To compare the clinical results of meniscal tears with arthroscopic results and to demonstrate the effectiveness of arthroscopy.

Project: A prospective study.

Place and duration of the study: In the Orthopedic Unit II of Nishtar Hospital Multan for one year duration from March 2019 to March 2020.

Patients and methods: The study consists of 74 patients. We examined a group of patients suspected of meniscus tears and focused on the most common findings related to medical history and meniscus injuries. Only clinically stable knees were selected and suspicion of anterior cruciate ligament (ACL) or posterior cruciate ligament tear (PCL) was excluded. All patients were selected from the outpatient clinic after careful clinical examination and basic research. When enrolled, relevant data from all patients was recorded. Appropriate clinical evaluation was made prior to arthroscopy. In all cases, a 30 degree arthroscope was used and arthroscopy was performed under general or spinal anesthesia with a compression band.

Results: The results of our study was that the accuracy rate of clinical diagnosis (77%) in comparison to that of arthroscopic diagnosis, signifies the diagnostic role of arthroscopy in meniscal tears.

Conclusion: It has been found that arthroscopy provides orthopedic surgeons with a very effective tool for diagnosing and treating meniscus tears.

Key words: meniscus tear, arthroscopy, anterior cruciate injury

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INTRODUCTION:

Trauma to the knee structures remains a diagnostic and therapeutic challenge. Arthroscopy has been shown to be an effective tool for diagnosing and treating knee pathologies. Arthroscopy is a safe and valuable procedure in diagnosing knee disorders. Knee arthroscopy in children and adolescents is safe, provides high diagnostic accuracy and enables the treatment of various intra-articular diseases. With the help of acute arthroscopy, damage to intra-articular structures or their combinations can be accurately diagnosed and treated. Depending on the results of arthroscopy, injuries can be treated immediately or operated on later, thus preventing further joint deterioration. A systematic approach is taken to establish anatomical and anatomical path correlations, as well as the role of arthroscopy in the diagnosis and treatment of meniscus injuries.

Half a century ago, Burman described the technique of knee, ankle and elbow arthroscopy, with a score of 30 knees. The lack of appropriate optical instruments prevented further expansion of arthroscopy. In 1959 Watnabe presented his arthroscope at No. 21, and arthroscopic meniscus surgery was initiated in 1960 by Watnabe and Ikeuchi. It has become a standard tool around the world for almost two decades, and in 1962, after great effort and research, he managed to perform the first arthroscopic meniscectomy. In the 1960s, this instrument was widely used in arthroscopy until the introduction of advanced arthroscopes. The advantage of this arthroscope was that it introduced a direct source of light into the joint. Arthroscopic meniscus surgery was documented by O'Connor in 1974.

In the '70s, DeHaven and others began performing open lumbar repair by posterior arthroscopy. Ikeuchi performed the first arthroscopic repair of the meniscus in Tokyo in 1979 and 1980; Henning performed the first arthroscopic repair in the United States.

Haus J et al. They conducted a study on 60 patients with acute knee joint injuries and concluded that, compared to arthroscopic diagnosis, clinical diagnosis was incorrect in about 45%. The most common clinical misdiagnosis was "medial meniscus tear". In a similar study, Ure BM, Tilling T et al. Reported the lowest accuracy of clinical diagnosis for meniscus changes; only 36% of meniscus tears were suspected before surgery

PATIENTS AND METHODS:

The patients included in the study were from 15 to 58 years of age. Out of total 74 patients, 13 were females and 61 males, between the ages of 15 and 58 years. 40 patients had symptoms in their right knee, 31 patients had problems in their left knee and

3 patients were with symptoms in both the knee joints with a total of 74 knees. The duration of symptoms lasted from a few weeks to a few months. The longest duration was 2 years. In most cases, arthroscopic examination was performed within two weeks of their first visit to us. During and before hospitalization, temperature, blood pressure, white blood cell counts, physical activity and other complications such as edema, pain, thrombosis and infection were checked. After discharge from the hospital, all patients were initially asked to visit the OPD once a week for 1 month, followed by a month after a total of six months. At each visit, patients were examined to observe any motor complications or restrictions and other data required for the study. Clinical diagnosis was based on careful medical history, physical examination and standard radiographs. The clinical diagnosis of internal knee disorders was unreliable because the signs and symptoms of injuries in various structures were generally similar. Limited movement with pain, muscle protection and tense swelling of the knee made it difficult to assess stability. Standard x-rays are usually not for diagnostic purposes. The common sensitivity of the line with signs of quadriceps wear is the most consistent and reliable sign of a torn meniscus. In recent injuries there has been swelling of the joint line of swelling shortly after the injury. McMurray's manoeuvre for medial meniscus, in which a click arising in the medial joint line accompanied by complaint of pain is indicative of medial meniscus tear. The McMurray maneuver for the lateral meniscus is a maneuver in which the sensation of the grating may be felt in the degenerative change of the meniscus.

Apley's grinding test 1 and 2 was performed on patients suspected of meniscus tears, and the suspected meniscus was subjected to compression and shear; sharp pain suggests a tear.

Meniscus cysts lie in the articular line, they feel pain when palpating, delicate under deep pressure. Meniscus cysts may be associated with tears. Lateral meniscus cysts are by far the most common. Swelling cysts on the medial side sometimes occur due to ganglia arising from pes anserinus.

The O Conn Connor classification of meniscus injury was adopted for the study:

The longitudinal tear is called longitudinal, because it is parallel to the edge of the meniscus. Total tears can move, and if they are moved over the interplatelet notch, this is called the tear of the spoon holder. If the tear is near the meniscus bag, it is a peripheral tear and is sutureable. Horizontal tears usually occur in the posterior half of the medial meniscus or in the middle of the lateral meniscus. It is common in the elderly. Oblique tears run

obliquely from the inner edge of the meniscus to her body. These are full thickness tears, which can be front or back. Radial tears are similar to oblique tears, except that they run from the inner edge to the outer edge of the meniscus.

Other varieties are lobular tears, complex tears and degenerative tears.

The treatment protocol was based on an accurate diagnosis of the meniscus tear and its immediate treatment leading to the cure and early recovery of the patient.

Strict rules were followed when selecting patients with OPD, and each patient was thoroughly examined and examined before being selected for examination.

After being selected for arthroscopy, the patient was admitted to the ward for further research and preoperative preparation. Clinical diagnosis was defined as "correct" when confirmed by arthroscopy. Clinical diagnosis was "incorrect" when arthroscopy showed a different diagnosis or additional and unexpected major lesion was found. Any additional findings observed during arthroscopic examination that were not related to the treatment of a given problem and were not disclosed during the clinical diagnosis do not necessarily make the clinical diagnosis "incorrect".

Anesthesia examination was performed prior to arthroscopic examination to further assess the integrity of intra-articular knee structures. Arthroscopy was performed using standard techniques in general anesthesia, spinal anesthesia in an aseptic operating room using a band in all patients. The knee area was shaved where required. Patients were placed on their backs with knees extended. This position is convenient for arthroscopes and prevents unnecessary obstruction during surgery.

After induction of anesthesia, the tourniquet was filled with a pressure of approximately 400 mm Hg. Anterolateral portal placed 1 cm above the lateral line of the joint and about 1 cm lateral to the edge of the patella tendon in a bent knee 30 degrees was selected for the initial introduction of the arthroscope and marked. Using a surgical knife blade (No. 11), a vertical incision was carefully made in the marked area through the skin, capsule

and synovium, maintaining the cutting direction of the knife edge up, thus avoiding damage to the intraarticular cartilage and meniscus in all patients. After careful insertion of the arthroscope through the portal, the articular space was inflated in all cases using normal saline. We preferred not to use air to inflate joints because of the risk of possible air embolism. Bottles with normal saline hung high above the level of the knee to maintain a constant pressure in the knee solution. During the arthroscopic examination, the knee joints were examined in the order: supravertebral and patellofemoral joint, medial gutter, medial compartment, interosseous excision, posterior-medial compartment, lateral and lateral gutter as well as lateral-lateral compartment.

RESULTS:

Simple x-rays of all patients were taken and no favorable signs of diagnosis were found. The only symptom that appeared was soft tissue inflammation, degenerative changes in bone and cartilage of the articular surfaces of the knee joint. All these patients underwent arthroscopic examination within two days of the last clinical examination. Arthroscopic examination showed the exact nature of the injury in the affected knee joints. In arthroscopy, meniscus changes were found in 57 knees (central meniscus 39, lateral meniscus 18). Additional findings, such as bilateral meniscus damage in 55 patients with meniscus rupture in 2 patients, partial ACL rupture in 3 patients, additional medial menisci in 2 patients and chondromalacia patella in 1 patient are 61 patients, 13 patients are women. 3 patients between 10 and 19 years old, 21 patients between 22 and 29 years old, 25 patients between 30 and 39 years old, 12 patients between 40 and 49 years old, 3 patients between 50 and 60 years old, 10 patients older than 60 years. Meniscus injuries were more common in the right knee (56.5%), and 79% of the patients were male. 54% of the medial tears of the meniscus are longitudinal tears, 24% horizontal tears, 12% oblique tears, 8% radial tears and 2% degenerative tears. The upper wings were six times more frequent than the lower ones. 6% of all fragments of the medial meniscus were reversed; 51% of them had a flap and the rest broke their ankle. 48% of lateral meniscus injuries are longitudinal tears, 29% horizontal tears, 16% radial tears, 5% oblique tears and 2% degenerative tears.

Figure: A. Bucket handle tear of medial meniscus.

Figure: B. Severe degeneration of lateral meniscus with tears of meniscus in marked osteoarthritis of knee

Figure: C. Longitudinal tear in posterior horn of lateral meniscus

Figure: D. Horizontal tear of lateral meniscus

In this prospective study focusing on meniscus damage, the overall success rate in the history of the disease and research was 74%. The total number of cases with clinical diagnosis was 74. Arthroscopic confirmed diagnosis was found in 57 (77%) patients. 17 (23%) patients had a poor clinical diagnosis.

DISCUSSION:

Seventy-four patients with symptoms of meniscus rupture were reviewed in this study. The study was conducted to emphasize the importance of arthroscopy in the diagnosis of meniscus tears. Test results showed only seventy-six percent accuracy of clinical results compared to arthroscopic results. In all cases, an arthroscope was used at an angle of 30 degrees. Arthroscopy was performed under general anesthesia, and the compression band under spinal anesthesia. The average time of diagnostic arthroscopy is 30 minutes. A single dose of antibiotic for injection was given prior to surgery followed by two postoperative doses. The next day, all patients were mobilized. Most patients were discharged the following day with a recommendation to regularly monitor OPD. The appearance of arthroscopy provided better visualization of the meniscus. The surgeon has access to all aspects of the meniscus, and managing meniscus tears has become much easier. Arthroscopy has important advantages over other surgical procedures in meniscus tears. Typical benefits include accurate diagnosis, smaller incision, less intense inflammatory response, reduced postoperative morbidity, no side effects, shorter hospital stays, very impressive results and reduced risk of complications, and early work. This study shows the diagnostic role of arthroscopy, since no serious complications were observed during the study, but several minor complications were observed, which were alleviated within a month of physical therapy and treatment. Therefore, in the light of this study, it has been shown that knee arthroscopy is a safe, reliable and useful method of diagnosing and treating meniscus lesions with low morbidity and minor complications. Knee arthroscopy is a minimally invasive surgery that can be performed in a children's room with minimal discomfort, reducing costs and reducing recovery time, making it an ideal technique for all trauma patients. The surgeon has access to all aspects of the meniscus. A common disadvantage is involuntary damage to the intra-articular structures. Instrumental rupture is also rare. Common complications are hemarthrosis, infections, thromboembolic diseases, ligament and neurological damage to intra-articular structures, menisci and fat pads, and cruciate ligaments. In 1986, Small reported 395,556 arthroscopic examinations with a total complication rate of 0.56%.

Greis PE et al. To sum up, the repair complications are neurological damage, postoperative loss of movement, recurrence of the rupture and infection. If the intra-articular pressure of the knee increases before the arthroscope is placed, damage to the inside of the knee can be significantly reduced. Thromboflebitis is really an important complication

in patients over 40 years of age. Arthroscopic meniscus surgery as a whole has an acceptably low percentage of complications. Williams JS Jr et al. The incidence of DVT has been shown to be 3.5% in postoperative patients. Habegger R et al. It is suggested to stop using air, especially in newly wounded joints. Broken instruments are primarily the surgeon's fault.

CONCLUSION:

Arthroscopic technique provided the orthopedic surgeon with a very powerful and very effective tool for diagnosing and treating meniscus tears. Arthroscopy offers unique benefits such as final diagnosis, smaller incision, less intense inflammatory response, reduced postoperative morbidity, no side effects, shorter hospital stays, very impressive results and reduced complication rate and early return to work. The frequency of complications is very rare and is not possible when it is performed by an experienced surgeon. Finally, this study concludes that arthroscopy is a safe and highly reliable method for diagnosing and treating meniscus tears with low morbidity and minor complications, making it an ideal technique for diagnosing and treating meniscus tears.

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